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PISA Predictive Power of Future Educational Attainments: A Longitudinal Study

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and Joel Rapp*

Abstract

PISA, the Program for International Student Assessment, is one of the most prominent cross-national standardized school exams conducted once every three years. The current study examines the extent to which the PISA Reading Proficiency (PRP) exam predicts future educational achievements among students tested in Israel in 2009. Overall, we find that Israel PISA 2009 is highly predictive of subsequent educational achievements. However, there is substantial variation across different educational measures.

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This study was conducted based on the Central Bureau of Statistics (CBS) databases. Nevertheless, it should be emphasized that this study is not an official publication of the CBS, and therefore the opinions and conclusions presented in this study do not necessarily reflect those of the CBS.

Introduction

PISA, the Program for International Student Assessment, is conducted by the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), and began testing students in 2000. Currently, more than 70 OECD countries and many partner countries participate in the study. Its goal is to assess 15-year-old students' level of literacy in mathematics, reading, and science, and their preparedness for the future.¹ The relatively large and representative samples alongside careful instrument design provide a strong basis for comparing educational outcomes across countries that can shape subsequent improvements in educational policy. This has been PISA's goal since its founding:

It aims to provide a new basis for policy dialogue and for collaboration in defining and implementing operationalizing educational goals, in innovative ways that reflect judgements about the skills that are relevant to adult life (OECD, 2004, p. 3).

PISA results are viewed in this manner. After every three-year cycle, national and international stakeholders study the reports and propose shifts in educational policy that are justified by anchoring them in PISA data, or their interpretation of those data (Zieger et al., 2022).

While PISA's ambitious goal is clear, there is insufficient information about the extent to which PISA achievements per-se actually relate to future educational attainment, or, in OECD report's words, "to what extent does PISA succeed in measuring 'skills for life?'" (OECD, 2003, p. 17). The main purpose of the present study is to address this issue using longitudinal data from Israel. We do this by following Israel's PISA 2009 examinees for 14 years, from the time they participated in PISA 2009 until they were 28–29-years-old, tracking their subsequent educational achievements in high school, their performance on their *Bagrut* (matriculation) exams, the Psychometric Entrance Test to Israeli universities (PET),² and entrance into — and graduation from — tertiary education. Our models also look at variation in these relationships of future educational attainment by examinees' gender, SES, and sector (Hebrew- vs. Arabic- speaking schools).

1 PISA participants are between the ages 15 years 3 months and 16 years 3 months.

2 The Israel PET assesses quantitative reasoning (40%), verbal reasoning (40%), and English as a foreign language (20%). It is used mainly for admission to university.

Literature review

Despite PISA's high global profile and more than two-decades long history of testing, research on PISA predictive power of subsequent adult-life outcomes is rather scarce. For example, in Luxembourg, PISA 2006 examinees were followed for five years: the predicted variable was the final exams (Fischbach et al., 2013). Overall, the findings confirm that PISA reading proficiency scores have significant predictive power regarding subsequent eligibility for the final exams. That relationship remained positive and statistically significant when researchers adjusted for examinees' socioeconomic background. The authors conclude that these findings are in line with PISA's claims that PISA reading proficiency scales are indeed an assessment of knowledge and skills for life rather than "knowledge and skills in assessment situations" as claimed by Dohn (2007). Similar results were found in a follow-up study on the relationships between PISA 2000 proficiency and eligibility for Bagrut certificate and postsecondary education in Germany (Ehmke, et al., 2008) and Canada (Knighton & Bussière, 2006). The latter found that level 5–6 examinees (the top scorers) are 2.65 more likely to study in higher education than are those on level 1 and below.

Another follow-up study was conducted in Denmark (SFI, 2014) by researchers from the Danish National Centre for Social Research (SFI). It merged PISA 2000 data with OECD PIAAC 2012 data — broadly, the latter measure skills of working age people across OECD countries. Strong links were found between cognitive skills assessed by PISA 2000 and higher education and transition to the labor market. Researchers ascribed 31% of the variance in Denmark's PIAAC results to the results of PISA 2000. A more recent study from New Zealand (Meehan et al., 2023) presents very similar findings, namely a very high correlation between the attainments in PISA and future success in adult life.

Overall, these longitudinal studies and others (e.g. OECD, 2018; Piacentini & Pacileo, 2019) confirm that PISA proficiencies, including reading proficiency, predict future academic achievements in general. In addition, they also point to the important roles of a number of demographic variables in accounting for future-life achievements and in being able to moderate, if not mediate, the apparent effects of PISA proficiencies. Each of these is also linked to a much larger corpus of research.

1. *Socioeconomic status*. The most well-found predictor of a student's future success at school — and, in many cases also access to well-paid and high-status occupations — is family background (e.g., Sirin, 2005; Broer et al., 2019). This is the case despite ongoing debate about how much of this underlying relationship can be attributed to different mechanisms.³ In either case, an important stratum within educational research, reflected in PISA results, shows that family status is not destiny. Across OECD countries, about one in ten low-SES students are “academically resilient:” they score in the top quarter of reading performance in their countries (OECD, 2019).
2. *Gender*. The gender gap differs in magnitude and direction across testing domains and countries. In all countries that participated in PISA 2009, girls significantly outperformed boys in reading, whereas boys outperformed girls in mathematics, but no significant gender differences were found in science literacy (OECD, 2010). Very similar results were found in previous and later PISA cycles, in 2000, 2003, 2006, 2012, 2015, and 2018 (see OECD, 2001; 2004; 2008; 2014; 2016; 2019, respectively). These conclusions are supported by other analyses (e.g., Guiso et al., 2008; Lietz, 2006; Rapp & Borgonovi, 2019).
3. *Educational sector*. In many countries, the educational system is not a single entity. In some, it includes different tracks (e.g., academic vs. technological). In others, it refers to differences in educational provider: private vs. public schools, or to religious vs. secular schools. In still others, it refers to different ethno-linguistic groups that the school serves, usually reflected in the main teaching language. Each of these characteristics can also overlap with population-based differences like level of education and wealth, and with regional distributions. In this study we refer to the one of the main divisions in the Israeli education system — namely, the Hebrew- and Arabic-speaking sectors.

3 That is, how much does the educational advantage of a child from a high SES family stem from access to better-quality schools, a family culture that places more emphasis on learning and self-discipline, and highly educated role models.

In sum, despite the small number of studies in this area and differences across countries, PISA generally predicts subsequent matriculation and entrance into universities, even after controlling for SES.⁴ However, this small array of studies has two key limitations. *First*, many of these studies cover a mere five years after participants completion of high school. That is far too small a time frame for assessing “skills that are relevant to adult life,” especially in Israel, where many young adults typically are engaged in their military service for at least 2–3 years, and then often take time off before heading into higher education. *Second*, previous studies did not consider possible contribution of the differences between subpopulations, which are especially important in the Israeli context, given the unique characteristics of Israeli society.

The specific goals of the present study arise from these considerations. In terms of the study time span, we follow Israel's 2009 PISA participants for about 14 years, from their participation in PISA 2009 at age 15–16 to age 28–29. As for the subpopulations, we focus on the two main groups in Israel — Hebrew speakers and Arabic speakers.

The study explores the relationships between examinees' achievements on PISA Reading Proficiency (PRP) and discrete measures of subsequent educational achievements (outcome variables⁵):

1. Eligibility for a certificate at the end of high school⁶ (being tested on the Bagrut exams/eligibility for a Bagrut certificate/eligibility for Bagrut certificate that meets higher education admission threshold);
2. Mean score on the Bagrut certificate⁷ (including/not including bonus);
3. Psychometric test (taking the psychometric test, and general psychometric score);

4 It does not always predict entrance into higher education in general. A second study using Canadian data finds that reading proficiency on the PISA 2000 exam was positively associated with entering universities, but not associated with entering colleges (Finnie & Mueller, 2009).

5 For a detailed explanation of the outcome variables, see the Appendix.

6 Bagrut certificate is a certificate, given by the Ministry of Education, based on a successful completion of a certain number of Bagrut exams, taken in the final years of high school.

7 The Bagrut mean score is calculated by the Ministry of Education as a weighted means of the various Bagrut exams.

4. Entrance to higher education (university/academic, college/academic, college for education/technology college/Haredi [ultra-Orthodox Jewish] women's teacher college);
5. Obtaining a bachelor's degree (university/academic college/academic college for education).

We draw attention to three main variables and analyze how the predictive power of PISA reading proficiency on these educational achievements fares after adjusting for examinees' SES,⁸ gender, and educational sector.

Methodology

The study merges PISA 2009 Israel data with a range of Israel Central Bureau of Statistics (CBS) data on the same individuals covering the 2009–2023 period. As implied by the aforementioned discrete educational outcome variables, these CBS data cover secondary school, tertiary education, and the performance on PET. In addition, the study analyzes the mediating roles of gender, SES, and sector.

Study sample

The original PISA 2009 study sample included 5,761 students in 176 schools, representing about 5.2% of the total 15–16-year-old cohort and 7.9% of Israel's middle and high schools. The final database for this study included 5,741 participants (20 examinees were lost due to technical problems). At the time of their PISA exam, 4,401 examinees were enrolled in schools where the language of instruction was Hebrew, and 1,340 were enrolled in schools where the language of instruction was Arabic.⁹ In each sector, examinees took the PISA exams in their respective language.

8 In this study, we use the Israel Central Bureau of Statistics (CBS) measure of students' SES in 2009 instead of the PISA measure "economic, social and cultural status" (ESCS) index. The two indices are highly correlated — 0.55 in these data — but the CBS measure is more highly correlated with PRP than is the ESCS: 0.44 versus 0.35, respectively.

9 The Arabic-speaking student population comprises of Arabs, Bedouins, and Druze, and Arabic language is the main language of instruction in their schools. The Hebrew educational sector includes secular, religious, and Haredi streams. The main language in all is Hebrew, with the exception of some Haredi schools. Notably, a small minority of Arab students (44 students which are about 3% of the Arabic-speaking examinees) studied in Hebrew-speaking schools, in this study, they were included in the Arab sector.

The gender breakdown in the original sample was 3,113 girls and 2,648 boys. This imbalance in the sample arises from the fact that Haredi boys' schools (educating about 7% of the population, RAMA, 2011) did not participate in PISA 2009.¹⁰

Explanatory variables

The core explanatory variable in this study is PISA Reading Proficiency (PRP) score in 2009.¹¹ PISA defines reading literacy as measuring "the capacity of a 15-year-old to understand, use and reflect on written texts [in order] to achieve personal goals, develop knowledge and potential, and participate in society."¹²

Israel's mean score on PRP 2009 was 474 (and standard deviation 112), about 20 points below the OECD PRP mean score (M = 493 and SD = 93). In addition, the gap between Israel's 5th and 95th percentiles was 365 points — compared to an OECD average gap of 305-points (OECD, 2010; RAMA, 2011) — indicating a very large disparity as explained hereafter.

PISA defines six main PRP levels and an additional level termed "below level 1," hereafter called "Level 0."¹³ In 2009, more than a quarter of Israel's examinees scored at the lowest levels: 15.1% were rated at Level 1 and 11.8% at Level 0. Only 7% of examinees scored at the highest levels, 5–6 (RAMA, 2011). In fact, Israel's 2009 examinees demonstrated wider variance in their scoring than in almost every other country, being surpassed by Qatar, Bulgaria, and Trinidad and Tobago (RAMA, 2011). This wide variance is consistent with Israel's performance in all other international standardized educational exams e.g., PIRLS, TIMSS, and other PISA studies.

10 Haredi boys' schools are Haredi Yeshiva institutes that emphasize religious studies and do not follow the official state curriculum, and, therefore, they usually do not participate in the PISA study.

11 In this study we used the reading-literacy scores because reading was the primary skill assessed in PISA 2009. Informal checks we conducted suggest that using mathematics or science scores instead of reading scores would not have materially changed the results.

12 See the OECD website, [Reading Performance \(PISA\)](#).

13 In principle in the present study we use the PISA reading proficiency (PRP) levels as in the PISA studies except for 1a and 1b used in PISA reports. For reasons of convenience, we termed PISA reading proficiency Level "1a" as Level "1" and "1b" and below as "below Level 1" or Level "0".

In the present study, we combined PISA Levels 5 and 6 (hereafter called Level 5) since the percent of Israel examinees on Level 6 was very small (1.01%). This combined category includes around 7% of examinees. In addition, regarding the Arabic-speaking sector, we combined PRP Levels 4 and 5 because of the very small percentage of Arabic-speaking examinees at Level 5 (0.3%). Thus, at the Arab-speaking sector, the highest PRP level is Level 4.

As in previous studies, the three other explanatory variables used in this study are SES (socio-economic status), gender, and sector (Hebrew-speaking schools versus Arabic-speaking schools).

Results

Figure 1 presents the distribution of reading proficiency levels by SES, gender, and sector. As shown in the figure, the most pronounced differences in reading levels are between students from high socioeconomic backgrounds and those from low socioeconomic backgrounds: students from more advantaged families tend to achieve higher reading scores compared with their peers from less advantaged backgrounds. With regard to gender, boys are overrepresented in low scores relative to girls. The sector differences are also substantial: 53.5% of Arabic-language students scored at the 0 or 1 level, as opposed to 17% of Hebrew-language students. This difference is also reflected at the other end of the score scale: only 0.3% of Arabic-language students scored at the highest level (5+), and 9.5% of Hebrew-language students. Due to this non-symmetric distribution between Hebrew-speaking and Arabic-speaking students, the descriptive findings are also presented by statistical quartiles of the PISA reading-score distribution within each sector (Appendix Table 4b), and the same applies to the results of the statistical models (Appendix Table 5).

Figure 1. Distribution of students according to PISA Reading Proficiency levels, by gender, sector and SES group

Source: Blass, Maagan, Mevarech, and Rapp, Taub Center | Data: CBS

Data in Table 1 show variation across PRP scores in a range of post-PISA measures of academic achievements. Three general patterns can be seen. *First*, there is a clear positive correlation between PRP scores and all subsequent educational attainment. Correlation coefficients are shown in Appendix Table 1. *Second*, the gradient of this relationship, as apparent by the increment between students' proportions (or scores) in adjacent PRP levels, is sharper on more selective measures than on less selective ones. Furthermore, on less selective measures, the gradient tends to flatten out, and, in some cases, even falls between Levels 4 and 5.

The *third* pattern indicates that among students who score at the lowest PRP levels, a non-trivial proportion, subsequently began studies at institutions of higher education: 10% of those who scored 0, and 25% of those who scored 1. Additionally, 5% of those who scored at Level 0 and 16% of those who scored at Level 1 received a first degree in higher education. Significant differences were also recorded among examinees at reading levels 3, 4, and 5 in the rates of those entering and receiving a degree from a university, whereas the differences among examinees at levels 0, 1, and 2 were smaller. This finding suggests that the correlation between reading literacy level and university education is stronger at the higher reading levels than at the lower ones.

Table 1. Educational achievements among 2009 PISA examinees, by reading proficiency score

Rate, unless otherwise indicated

	TOTAL	PISA Reading Proficiency level					
		0	1	2	3	4	5
High school achievement							
Bagrut exams							
Took Bagrut exams	0.89	0.62	0.81	0.88	0.92	0.94	0.96
Eligible for a Bagrut certificate	0.63	0.28	0.48	0.65	0.81	0.90	0.95
Eligible for a Bagrut certificate that meets higher education admission threshold	0.47	0.10	0.21	0.41	0.64	0.80	0.90
Mean score on the Bagrut exams (pts.)							
Mean score	75.68	61.7	66.5	72.3	78.0	83.1	87.2
Mean score including bonus	84.21	65.2	71.8	79.3	87.2	94.7	100.2
Psychometric exam							
Took the psychometric exam	0.38	0.06	0.17	0.28	0.45	0.60	0.68
General psychometric score (pts.)	554	392	435	475	540	611	659
Entrance to higher education	0.50	0.10	0.25 ^a	0.41	0.62	0.76	0.84
Higher education by institution							
University	0.25	0.04	0.10	0.16	0.26	0.45	0.59
Academic college	0.20	0.04	0.10	0.18	0.28	0.24	0.20
Academic college for education	0.05	0.01	0.03	0.05	0.08	0.06	0.05
Technology school	0.06	0.05	0.09	0.08	0.05	0.06	0.03
Haredi women's teacher college	0.06	0.01	0.04	0.06	0.07	0.08	0.05
Degree study major							
Humanities	0.06	0.02	0.03	0.05	0.07	0.09	0.11
Social sciences	0.20	0.04	0.11	0.19	0.23	0.28	0.28
Natural sciences	0.18	0.01	0.04	0.10	0.21	0.34	0.45
Completed first degree							
University	0.38	0.05	0.16	0.30	0.46	0.59	0.72
Academic college	0.18	0.01	0.05	0.10	0.17	0.35	0.54
Academic college for education	0.16	0.03	0.08	0.15	0.22	0.20	0.15
Academic college for education	0.04	0.01	0.02	0.05	0.07	0.04	0.02

Notes: Students who take the Bagrut exams at higher levels (4 or 5 study units) receive bonus points. Detailed findings are presented in Appendix Table 2 to Appendix Table 4.

Source: Blass, Maagan, Mevarech, and Rapp, Taub Center | Data: CBS

Multivariate models

To examine the relationships between PRP scores and measures of subsequent educational achievements while also accounting for the effects of gender, educational sector, and students' SES, we performed a series of regressions on the above discrete dependent variables. The results are shown in Table 2. In the regressions, men were coded 1 and women 0, Hebrew-speaking examinees were coded 1 and Arabic-speaking examinees were coded 0, SES was treated as a continuous variable, and each of the PRP Levels 1–5 were compared to PRP Level 0.

For simplicity and ease of comparison, we intentionally specify a parsimonious OLS model that is identical across the dependent variables, including where the dependent variable is dichotomous and indicative of completion of an educational target (Bagrut certificate, participation in PET exams, entrance to higher education, and receipt of a first degree). In addition to PRP levels, the model includes three demographic controls: the examinee's SES level at the time of the exam — a continuous variable (see footnote 8 previously), educational sector, and gender.

For ease in interpretation, we present the beta coefficients (standardized coefficients). Additionally, since almost all coefficients are statistically significant at the $p < 0.0001$ level, we only note coefficients' significance where they fall below that level (values in purple indicate a significance level of $p < 0.05$ while those in red are not statistically significant).

Table 2. Findings from a regression model: Estimates of the factors explaining the academic achievements of PISA examinees by reading proficiency levels

Model	High school achievements				Psychometric exams		Higher education	
	Eligible for a Bagrut certificate	Eligible for a Bagrut certificate that meets higher education admission threshold	Mean Bagrut score	Mean Bagrut score incl. bonus	Took the psychometric exam	General psychometric score	Entrance to higher education	Completed first degree
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)
SES								
SES	0.122	0.160	0.139	0.154	0.206	0.231	0.215	0.186
Gender (Reference group: Girls)								
Boys	-0.260	-0.014	-0.033	-0.021	-0.052	0.202	-0.071	-0.137
Sector (Reference group: Arabic speaking)								
Hebrew speaking	-0.064	-0.160	-0.149	-0.209	-0.310	-0.018	-0.068	-0.099
PISA reading proficiency level (Reference group: 0)								
1	0.144	0.077	0.135	0.146	0.084	0.081	0.082	0.053
2	0.322	0.265	0.356	0.379	0.216	0.259	0.211	0.174
3	0.493	0.487	0.577	0.622	0.380	0.543	0.385	0.300
4	0.500	0.551	0.660	0.723	0.448	0.777	0.417	0.354
5	0.362	0.419	0.532	0.581	0.338	0.710	0.308	0.297
Constant	0.363	0.239	65.21	70.72	0.336	382.9	0.255	0.253
N	4,992	4,992	4,833	4,833	5,634	2,205	5,634	5,634
Adjusted R ²	0.191	0.272	0.332	0.386	0.232	0.481	0.246	0.205

Notes: All models are estimated in OLS. The beta coefficients presented in the table are standardized coefficients. All coefficients are statistically significant at $p < 0.0001$, except for the values marked in purple, which indicate a significance level of $p < 0.05$, and the values marked in red, which are not statistically significant. Appendix Table 5 presents the results of the statistical models by statistical quartiles of the PISA reading-score distribution.

Source: Blass, Maagan, Mevarech, and Rapp, Taub Center | Data: CBS

The three demographic controls each point to a statistically and substantively important effect. Among these three, SES had the highest contribution to future educational achievement. In all eight models, the coefficients are positive and significant, ranging from 0.12 to 0.23 standard deviations (SD). In other words,

net of other controls in the model, a one SD increase in a person's SES is associated with a 0.15 SD increase in their Bagrut including bonus points, a 0.21 SD increase in their likelihood of taking the psychometric test, a 0.23 SD increase in their score on that psychometric test, and so on.

In all models, the beta coefficients of sector are negative. In other words, in any given PRP level — the future educational achievements of PISA's Hebrew language examinees are systematically lower than the Arabic-language examinees. These differences range from one tenth of a standard deviation or less (eligible for Bagrut certificate; PET score, entrance to higher education) to two tenths of a standard deviation or higher (Bagrut score including bonus; taking the psychometric test). Furthermore, the beta coefficients of gender are negative and statistically significant in five of the eight models, indicating that men tend to have worse subsequent educational achievements than do women. The one notable exception to this is their score on the psychometric test; men are less likely to take it (Model 5), but if they do, their average score is 0.23 SDs higher than the score for women.

The most interesting findings would be the high contributions of PRP levels to all educational achievements' variables, controlling for participants' demographic background. The predictive power of the PRP levels is much stronger than that of participants' demographic characteristics, especially for PRP levels 2 and higher. The beta coefficients at PRP 2 range from 0.17 SD to 0.38. At PRP 3, they range from 0.3 to 0.62, and at PRP 4 from 0.35 to 0.78. Interestingly, the range then falls at highest PRP 5 level, in most cases below PRP 3 estimates.

Finally, comparing the percentage of explained variance by PRP levels across the dependent variables raises several interesting results. With regard to high school achievements, the explained variance ranged from 19% (eligible for Bagrut certificate) to 39% (Bagrut mean score including bonus points). Regarding the psychometric test, the explained variance was 23% and 48% on taking the test and its score, respectively. On tertiary education, the explained variance was 25% and 20% regarding starting higher education and graduating, respectively. Across these categories, the explained variance is higher on the mean Bagrut scores including bonus; and psychometric test score — two indices that are used for entrance to Israeli universities.

Beyond these patterns, the beta coefficients are lower for Hebrew-speakers and men than for Arabic speakers and women. The score on the psychometric test is the only exception to this, especially for gender.

In summary, PISA scores are highly predictive of subsequent academic achievements. They are especially predictive of the mean Bagrut scores including bonus, and the general psychometric score.

Discussion

Our study explores the extent to which PISA reading proficiency predicts future educational achievements regarding participants' high school outcomes, psychometric entrance test scores, and tertiary education, controlling for gender, SES and sector. To explore these issues, we analyzed the educational outcomes of almost all PISA 2009 examinees.

Our findings, which are in line with the findings presented in the literature review, point to the significant relationships between reading proficiency assessed by PISA 2009 and participants' future academic achievements. An interesting effect revealed in this research is relatively high percentage of the low achievers who, in contrast to expectations, succeeded in the later stages of their academic career. Against all odds, about a half of examinees at Level 1 and almost third at Level 0 were eligible for the Bagrut certificate; 25% of students at Reading Level 1 and 10% of those at Reading Level 0 entered some form of higher education; and 16% of students at Level 1 and 5% of those at Level 0 earned a bachelor's degree.

The relationship between PISA scores and academic achievements was much stronger than the demographic variables assessed in this study (SES, gender, and language sector). This was evident even after controlling for these demographic variables.

Several factors may explain these findings in the Israeli context. First, the Israeli education system puts a lot of effort into narrowing disparities and creating equal opportunities in education. Almost all high schools provide special classes to prepare low achievers for the Bagrut exams; provide additional Bagrut exam opportunities for those with failing scores; and in the geographic periphery, colleges have been opened to advance equal opportunities to enroll in higher education. In addition to high school programs, the universities and colleges themselves provide help for those who face difficulties, including preparatory courses for academic studies, mentors, additional practice classes, and more. In this context, it is worth mentioning

the Open University, which does not have specific admission requirements, thereby provides additional opportunities for acquiring higher education even for those who do not hold a Bagrut certificate. Thus, educational policy could assist in the transition from high school education to tertiary education, and maybe also integrating into the labor markets (OECD, 2010).

From the three demographic variables, SES had the strongest effects on all dependent variables (measures of future educational outcomes). As shown in Table 2 and Appendix Table 2, at all comparable PRP levels, students who come from high SES families scored significantly higher on reading proficiency and had better future educational achievements than students who come from low SES families. The findings regarding the middle SES group indicates that there is some social mobility in Israel, while the lowest SES group had lower achievements.

Gender differences varied by dependent variable. Girls outperformed boys on PRP (by 0.40 SD). Data from Table 2 and from Appendix Table 3 show that in the majority of reading achievement levels, a larger proportion of women began studying in academic colleges or academic colleges of education. In contrast, at the higher achievement levels (Level 3+) boys enrolled in universities at higher rates than girls. In addition, at all achievement levels, girls outperformed boys in proportions taking the psychometric test but boys attained higher scores on the tests and a higher proportion of them studied natural sciences in institutions of higher education. It seems that girls' higher scores on PRP result in higher admission rates to tertiary education, but not in choosing fields that have the potential for future greater income. The advantage of women in entering tertiary education (at all PRP levels) is in line with previous studies showing that in Israel, as in many other OECD countries, women tend to attend tertiary education at a higher rate than men.¹⁴

Finally, we wish to draw attention to another important finding of this study, concerning the outcomes of Arabic-speaking students. We find that the outcomes for Arabic-speaking students are better than those for Hebrew-speaking students at every reading-proficiency level from 0 to 4. However, this finding contradicts the overall result showing that, on average (beyond reading-levels), Hebrew-speaking examinees achieve higher outcomes than Arabic-speaking examinees. For example, the share eligible for a Bagrut certificate

14 See Statistical Abstract of Israel 2021 (No.72), table 4.69, *Students at institutions of higher education,(1) by degree,(2) sex, age, population group, and district of residence.*

that meets the admission requirements for higher education was 50% among Hebrew speakers compared to 39% among Arabic speakers, and similarly across most achievement measures (Appendix Table 4a). The explanation for this contradiction lies in the distribution of examinees across reading proficiency levels (Figure 1 above): among Arabic-speaking examinees, most (about 79%) are concentrated in reading Levels 0–2, with only a small percent in Level 4 and just 0.3% in Level 5. In contrast, among Hebrew-speaking examinees, most (about 62%) are concentrated in reading Levels 3–5, with only a small share in Level 0. The descriptive findings and the statistical models are presented by quartiles of the PISA reading test scores (Appendix Tables 4b and 5).

Limitations and suggestions for future research

The present study presents unique findings, particularly those related to the lower PRP achievers (Level 1 and below) and the Arabic-speaking sector. Nevertheless, the study has some limitations that may be addressed in future research.

First, the present study focused only on the relationships between reading proficiency and academic achievements: high school, PET, and tertiary education. One can ask to what extent does PISA reading proficiency (or math/science proficiency)¹⁵ scores predict future achievements in other domains, such as employment or wages?

Second, the present study analyzed PISA 2009 reading literacy, without relating to other social competency factors that are important in the 21st century, such as collaborative problem solving or creative thinking. PISA was aware of this drawback and added one-off assessments in each cycle, like collaborative problem solving (2015 cycle), global competence (2018 cycle), and creative thinking (2022 cycle). Future research may repeat our study by focusing on these sorts of measures in addition to literacy, mathematics, or science literacy.

Finally, the present study analyzed only Israeli data. Since each country has unique cultural characteristics and different educational system, a comparison study is needed to examine the extent to which these findings can be generalized to educational systems in other countries.

15 As noted, in this study we have used reading literacy scores because in PISA 2009 that was the main literacy subject of the study.

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Appendix

Outcome measures

The dependent variables in this study are intended to measure educational outcomes of PISA examinees at three later stages of their academic careers: in high school, on the psychometric test, and at the higher education level. High-School achievements include: (1) being tested on the Bagrut exam; (2) eligibility for a Bagrut certificate; (3) eligibility for a “high quality Bagrut certificate” that meets higher education (primarily universities) admission threshold; (4) the mean score on the Bagrut exams; and (5) mean score on the Bagrut exams including bonus.

Eligibility for a Bagrut certificate is determined by a “passing score” on a minimum number of study-units and on seven compulsory disciplines. Eligibility for Bagrut certificate that meets higher education admission threshold depends on higher level of English studies (as a foreign language) and of mathematics.

The Bagrut mean score, which ranges from 0 to 100, is calculated by the weighted means corresponding to the study units of all the exams taken by a student. This score is one of the criteria used for admission to tertiary education (the other is the PET score described below). Students taking the Bagrut exams at higher levels (4 or 5 study units) receive bonus points to their scores. Due to the bonuses method, students can receive a mean Bagrut score higher than 100. In the current study, we analyze the mean Bagrut scores both including and not including bonus.

Psychometric Entrance Test (PET) is an SAT-like test (in the US) that includes three parts: verbal reasoning (40%), quantitative reasoning (40%), and English as a foreign language (20%). In most university faculties, the test score in combination with the Bagrut average score is an entrance requirement. Thus, taking the psychometric test testifies, to a large extent, an intention to attend an academic institution of higher education, primarily university. In general, less than 40% of a given cohort in Israel takes the test. In this study, we used the total PET score (composed of the three domains' score). In cases where candidates took the PET more than once, we used the best score for the analyses.

Tertiary Education in this study refers to post-secondary studies including universities, colleges, colleges of education, 2-year technology institutions, and 2-year Haredi women's teacher college. Universities, colleges, and colleges of education provide a bachelor's degree, whereas the 2-year institutions provide a non-academic certificate. In addition, the present study analyzes also the domains that the participants chose to study: humanities, social sciences, and natural sciences.

Appendix Table 1. Pearson correlation coefficients between PRP 2009 and subsequent educational achievements, by SES, gender, and sector

Rate, unless otherwise indicated

	TOTAL	Exam language		Gender		SES		
		Arabic	Hebrew	Girls	Boys	Low	Medium	High
High school achievements								
Bagrut exams								
Took Bagrut exams	0.29	0.33	0.30	0.14	0.39	0.11	0.25	0.29
Eligible for a Bagrut certificate	0.43	0.44	0.40	0.40	0.45	0.38	0.38	0.34
Eligible for a Bagrut certificate that meets higher education admission threshold	0.50	0.51	0.50	0.49	0.50	0.42	0.44	0.44
Mean score on the Bagrut certificate (pts.)								
Mean score	0.56	0.52	0.58	0.58	0.53	0.45	0.55	0.55
Mean score including bonus	0.60	0.56	0.63	0.60	0.59	0.49	0.58	0.59
Psychometric exam								
Took the psychometric exam	0.40	0.55	0.43	0.37	0.40	0.29	0.35	0.38
General psychometric score (pts.)	0.63	0.54	0.56	0.65	0.68	0.55	0.58	0.54

Appendix Table 1 (continued). Pearson correlation coefficients between PRP 2009 and subsequent educational achievements, by SES, gender, and sector

Rate, unless otherwise indicated

	TOTAL	Exam language		Gender		SES		
		Arabic	Hebrew	Girls	Boys	Low	Medium	High
Entrance to higher education	0.47	0.47	0.44	0.41	0.50	0.36	0.40	0.38
Higher education by institution								
University	0.36	0.35	0.35	0.32	0.39	0.20	0.31	0.34
Academic college	0.17	0.18	0.12	0.13	0.19	0.21	0.13	0.02
Academic college for education	0.07	0.15	0.05	0.04	0.06	0.12	0.07	0.00
Technology school	-0.03	0.05	-0.04	0.06	-0.07	0.07	-0.04	-0.12
Haredi women's teacher college	0.08	—	0.04	0.05	0.01	0.26	0.09	0.01
Degree study major								
Humanities	0.12	0.15	0.13	0.12	0.08	0.06	0.11	0.10
Social sciences	0.20	0.15	0.17	0.16	0.19	0.19	0.15	0.08
Natural sciences	0.34	0.35	0.32	0.31	0.39	0.25	0.30	0.28
Completed first degree	0.42	0.44	0.40	0.39	0.41	0.33	0.32	0.37
University	0.36	0.34	0.36	0.36	0.36	0.22	0.27	0.38
Academic college	0.15	0.18	0.12	0.11	0.16	0.19	0.12	0.03
Academic teachers college	0.05	0.14	0.04	0.03	0.02	0.12	0.05	0.01

Appendix Table 2. Educational achievements among PISA 2009 examinees, by reading proficiency score and student SES

Rate, unless otherwise indicated

	PISA Reading Proficiency Level																				
	TOTAL			0			1			2 SES			3			4			5		
	Low	Med.	High	Low	Med.	High	Low	Med.	High	Low	Med.	High	Low	Med.	High	Low	Med.	High	Low	Med.	High
High school achievements																					
Bagrut exams																					
Took Bagrut exams	0.80	0.90	0.95	0.70	0.64	0.57	0.82	0.82	0.87	0.85	0.90	0.91	0.82	0.94	0.98	0.78	0.95	0.98	0.78	0.94	0.99
Eligible for a Bagrut certificate	0.45	0.65	0.80	0.27	0.30	0.33	0.44	0.48	0.60	0.61	0.64	0.72	0.77	0.80	0.84	0.79	0.88	0.93	0.88	0.94	0.95
Eligible for a Bagrut certificate that meets higher education admission threshold	0.28	0.47	0.67	0.09	0.12	0.09	0.19	0.17	0.33	0.37	0.40	0.46	0.60	0.60	0.69	0.62	0.77	0.86	0.77	0.85	0.93
Mean score on the Bagrut exams (pts.)																					
Mean score	70.77	75.25	79.83	61.5	59.3	66.3	65.5	66.5	69.5	71.7	71.9	73.7	77.6	77.5	78.7	82.1	82.3	83.8	84.2	86.3	87.8
Mean score including bonus	77.64	83.53	89.87	65.0	62.6	69.3	71.0	71.5	75.7	79.0	78.7	80.6	86.7	86.2	88.4	92.6	93.6	95.7	95.5	99.2	101.1
Psychometric exam																					
Took the psychometric exam	0.26	0.35	0.52	0.06	0.04	0.10	0.19	0.14	0.22	0.32	0.26	0.27	0.38	0.40	0.54	0.45	0.54	0.67	0.40	0.64	0.72
General psychometric score (pts.)	474	545	598	385	387	426	407	442	497	447	480	519	500	531	565	581	597	622	614	650	665

Appendix Table 2 (continued). Educational achievements among PISA 2009 examinees, by reading proficiency score and student SES

Rate, unless otherwise indicated

	PISA Reading Proficiency Level																				
	TOTAL			0			1			2			3			4			5		
	Low	Med.	High	Low	Med.	High	Low	Med.	High	Low	Med.	High	Low	Med.	High	Low	Med.	High	Low	Med.	High
Entrance to higher education	0.29	0.51	0.70-	0.08	0.13	0.15	0.19	0.25	0.43	0.34	0.40	0.52	0.44	0.62	0.74	0.59	0.72	0.82	0.60	0.80	0.88
Higher education by institution																					
University	0.12	0.24	0.39	0.04	0.04	0.08	0.09	0.11	0.16	0.14	0.14	0.22	0.18	0.26	0.32	0.27	0.42	0.52	0.27	0.51	0.66
Academic college	0.12	0.21	0.27	0.03	0.07	0.06	0.06	0.10	0.23	0.14	0.20	0.24	0.19	0.27	0.35	0.27	0.20	0.26	0.15	0.25	0.18
Academic teacher college	0.05	0.07	0.05	0.01	0.01	—	0.03	0.05	0.03	0.06	0.05	0.06	0.07	0.09	0.07	0.05	0.10	0.04	0.18	0.04	0.03
Technological college	0.07	0.07	0.05	0.04	0.05	0.12	0.07	0.11	0.10	0.09	0.08	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.04	0.12	0.07	0.03	0.10	0.05	0.02
Haredi women's teacher college	0.11	0.06	0.01	0.01	—	—	0.05	0.04	0.01	0.11	0.06	0.02	0.18	0.07	0.01	0.34	0.09	0.01	0.22	0.10	0.02
Degree study major																					
Humanities	0.04	0.05	0.09	0.02	0.02	—	0.02	0.01	0.07	0.04	0.05	0.04	0.05	0.06	0.09	0.06	0.08	0.11	0.03	0.10	0.12
Social sciences	0.12	0.19	0.28	0.03	0.06	0.09	0.09	0.11	0.21	0.14	0.18	0.28	0.18	0.23	0.27	0.22	0.23	0.32	0.17	0.27	0.30
Natural sciences	0.08	0.17	0.29	0.01	—	0.06	0.02	0.06	0.09	0.07	0.10	0.13	0.12	0.20	0.28	0.26	0.30	0.38	0.28	0.46	0.46
Completed first degree	0.22	0.36	0.54	0.08	0.16	0.15	0.13	0.16	0.43	0.26	0.30	0.52	0.34	0.43	0.74	0.50	0.51	0.82	0.51	0.66	0.88
University	0.07	0.16	0.30	—	0.02	0.01	0.04	0.06	0.06	0.07	0.10	0.14	0.09	0.15	0.23	0.22	0.29	0.42	0.30	0.43	0.61
Academic college	0.11	0.15	0.21	0.03	0.06	0.04	0.06	0.07	0.16	0.13	0.14	0.19	0.17	0.20	0.27	0.22	0.16	0.22	0.15	0.20	0.14
Academic teacher college	0.04	0.05	0.03	0.01	—	—	0.03	0.03	0.01	0.05	0.06	0.04	0.08	0.08	0.06	0.07	0.06	0.02	0.06	0.03	0.02

Source: Blass, Maagan, Mevarech, and Rapp, Taub Center | Data: CBS

Appendix Table 3. Educational achievements among PISA 2009 examinees, by reading proficiency score and gender
Rate, unless otherwise indicated

	PISA Reading Proficiency Level													
	TOTAL		0		1		2		3		4		5	
	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys
High school achievements														
Bagrut exams														
Took Bagrut exams	0.89	0.88	0.75	0.56	0.83	0.80	0.89	0.87	0.91	0.95	0.92	0.97	0.94	0.99
Eligible for a Bagrut certificate	0.67	0.60	0.29	0.28	0.48	0.47	0.68	0.61	0.81	0.81	0.9	0.90	0.96	0.93
Bagrut certificate that meets higher education admission threshold	0.51	0.43	0.08	0.11	0.20	0.22	0.43	0.39	0.65	0.63	0.81	0.79	0.89	0.90
Mean score on the Bagrut exams (pts.)														
Mean score	76.94	74.28	59.5	63.1	65.8	67.1	73.3	71.3	78.6	77.2	84.2	81.8	87.5	86.8
Mean score including bonus	85.79	82.48	63.2	66.4	71.2	72.3	80.6	78.1	87.7	86.5	95.6	93.6	100.23	100.3
Psychometric exam														
Took the psychometric exam	0.43	0.32	0.08	0.05	0.20	0.16	0.33	0.24	0.46	0.44	0.62	0.56	0.73	0.59
General psychometric score (pts.)	538	579	367	412	405	463	460	496	512	583	593	638	642	690

Appendix Table 3 (continued). Educational achievements among PISA 2009 examinees, by reading proficiency score and gender

Rate, unless otherwise indicated

	PISA Reading Proficiency Level													
	TOTAL		0		1		2		3		4		5	
	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys
Entrance to higher education	0.56	0.44	0.13	0.08	0.28	0.23	0.47	0.34	0.64	0.60	0.75	0.77	0.86	0.80
Higher education by institution														
University	0.26	0.24	0.06	0.03	0.10	0.10	0.18	0.15	0.24	0.29	0.42	0.51	0.60	0.59
Academic college	0.22	0.17	0.06	0.04	0.12	0.09	0.21	0.16	0.28	0.28	0.25	0.24	0.22	0.16
Academic teacher college	0.08	0.03	0.02	—	0.04	0.03	0.08	0.02	0.12	0.03	0.08	0.03	0.05	0.05
Technological college	0.05	0.08	—	0.06	0.03	0.14	0.06	0.10	0.04	0.07	0.08	0.02	0.04	0.03
Haredi women's teacher college	0.11	0.01	0.01	—	0.08	0.01	0.12	0.01	0.12	0.01	0.13	—	0.08	0.01
Degree study major														
Humanities	0.09	0.03	0.03	0.01	0.03	0.02	0.06	0.03	0.10	0.03	0.11	0.06	0.15	0.05
Social sciences	0.25	0.14	0.07	0.03	0.15	0.08	0.24	0.13	0.28	0.16	0.29	0.26	0.35	0.18
Natural sciences	0.15	0.21	—	0.01	0.02	0.06	0.07	0.12	0.14	0.32	0.29	0.41	0.38	0.54
Completed first degree	0.46	0.28	0.07	0.04	0.20	0.12	0.38	0.22	0.52	0.36	0.64	0.52	0.76	0.66
University	0.20	0.16	0.01	0.01	0.04	0.05	0.11	0.09	0.16	0.17	0.35	0.34	0.54	0.54
Academic college	0.19	0.12	0.05	0.02	0.12	0.05	0.18	0.12	0.24	0.18	0.22	0.17	0.19	0.10
Academic teacher college	0.07	0.01	0.01	—	0.04	0.01	0.09	0.01	0.11	0.01	0.06	0.01	0.03	0.01

Source: Blass, Maagan, Mevarech, and Rapp, Taub Center | Data: CBS

Appendix Table 4a. Educational achievements among PISA 2009 examinees, by reading proficiency score and language of exam

Rate, unless otherwise indicated

	PISA Reading Proficiency Level													
	TOTAL		0		1		2		3		4		5	
	Exam language													
	Arabic	Hebrew	Arabic	Hebrew	Arabic	Hebrew	Arabic	Hebrew	Arabic	Hebrew	Arabic	Hebrew	Arabic	Hebrew
High school achievements														
Took Bagrut exams														
Took Bagrut exams	0.90	0.89	0.68	0.54	0.87	0.77	0.95	0.86	0.97	0.92	0.95	0.94	0.96	
Eligible for a Bagrut certificate	0.52	0.66	0.24	0.35	0.52	0.44	0.69	0.63	0.81	0.81	0.98	0.89	0.95	
Eligible for a Bagrut certificate that meets higher education admission threshold	0.39	0.50	0.10	0.10	0.29	0.15	0.53	0.36	0.74	0.62	0.96	0.79	0.90	
Mean score on the Bagrut exams (pts.)														
Mean score	72.48	76.59	61.06	62.62	68.38	65.01	75.20	71.15	81.43	77.40	88.84	82.81	87.18	
Mean score including bonus	81.04	85.12	65.25	65.19	75.16	69.13	84.76	77.17	93.52	86.10	104.08	94.15	100.24	
Psychometric exam														
Took the psychometric exam	0.43	0.36	0.08	0.03	0.31	0.08	0.57	0.18	0.79	0.39	0.91	0.58	0.68	
General psychometric score (pts.)	481	580	389	405	422	470	453	500	525	545	623	610	659	

Appendix Table 4a (continued). Educational achievements among PISA 2009 examinees, by reading proficiency score and language of exam

Rate, unless otherwise indicated

	PISA Reading Proficiency Level														
	TOTAL		0		1		2		3		4		5		
			Exam language												
	Arabic	Hebrew	Arabic	Hebrew	Arabic	Hebrew	Arabic	Hebrew	Arabic	Hebrew	Arabic	Hebrew	Hebrew		
Entrance to higher education	0.34	0.55	0.07	0.12	0.26	0.24	0.41	0.41	0.64	0.62	0.83	0.75	0.84		
Higher education by institution															
University	0.18	0.27	0.03	0.04	0.14	0.08	0.20	0.15	0.31	0.25	0.70	0.44	0.59		
Academic college	0.10	0.23	0.03	0.06	0.08	0.12	0.14	0.20	0.20	0.29	0.07	0.25	0.20		
Academic college for education	0.06	0.05	0.01	0.01	0.04	0.03	0.07	0.05	0.12	0.07	0.06	0.06	0.05		
Technology school	0.07	0.06	0.04	0.05	0.09	0.09	0.09	0.08	0.05	0.05	0.09	0.05	0.03		
Haredi women's teacher college	—	0.07	—	0.01	—	0.06	—	0.08	—	0.08	—	0.08	0.05		
Degree study major															
Humanities	0.06	0.06	0.02	0.02	0.05	0.01	0.08	0.03	0.11	0.06	0.16	0.09	0.11		
Social sciences	0.11	0.22	0.03	0.05	0.11	0.11	0.14	0.20	0.16	0.25	0.16	0.29	0.28		
Natural sciences	0.10	0.20	0.01	0.02	0.04	0.04	0.10	0.10	0.25	0.21	0.50	0.33	0.45		
Completed first degree	0.28	0.41	0.04	0.05	0.18	0.14	0.36	0.28	0.52	0.45	0.77	0.58	0.41		
University	0.12	0.20	0.01	0.01	0.06	0.04	0.13	0.09	0.21	0.16	0.65	0.33	0.54		
Academic college	0.11	0.17	0.03	0.04	0.09	0.08	0.16	0.14	0.20	0.22	0.07	0.21	0.15		
Academic college for education	0.05	0.04	—	—	0.03	0.01	0.07	0.04	0.10	0.06	0.05	0.04	0.02		

Source: Blass, Maagan, Mevarech, and Rapp, Taub Center | Data: CBS

Appendix Table 4b. Educational achievements among PISA 2009 examinees, by PISA reading quartile and language of exam

Rate, unless otherwise indicated

	PISA Reading Proficiency Quartile									
	TOTAL		1		2		3		4	
	Arabic	Hebrew	Arabic	Hebrew	Exam language		Arabic	Hebrew	Arabic	Hebrew
	Arabic	Hebrew	Arabic	Hebrew	Arabic	Hebrew	Arabic	Hebrew	Arabic	Hebrew
High school achievements										
Took Bagrut exams										
Took Bagrut exams	0.90	0.89	0.77	0.78	0.88	0.90	0.95	0.92	0.97	0.95
Eligible for a Bagrut certificate	0.52	0.66	0.19	0.36	0.43	0.65	0.64	0.78	0.80	0.88
Eligible for a Bagrut certificate that meets higher education admission threshold	0.39	0.50	0.07	0.15	0.24	0.43	0.47	0.63	0.73	0.81
Mean score on the Bagrut exams (pts.)										
Mean score	72.48	76.59	60.71	66.04	67.55	74.04	74.20	79.07	82.17	85.08
Mean score including bonus	81.04	85.12	64.86	70.34	74.01	81.10	83.44	88.69	94.54	97.33
Psychometric exam										
Took the psychometric exam	0.43	0.36	0.09	0.09	0.29	0.27	0.53	0.45	0.79	0.64
General psychometric score (pts.)	481	580	389	481	410	510	452	570	536	633

Appendix Table 4b (continued). Educational achievements among PISA 2009 examinees, by PISA reading quartile and language of exam

Rate, unless otherwise indicated

	PISA Reading Proficiency Quartile									
	TOTAL		1		2		3		4	
	Arabic	Hebrew	Arabic	Hebrew	Exam language		Arabic	Hebrew	Arabic	Hebrew
	Arabic	Hebrew	Arabic	Hebrew	Arabic	Hebrew	Arabic	Hebrew	Arabic	Hebrew
Entrance to higher education	0.34	0.55	0.07	0.24	0.25	0.51	0.37	0.66	0.65	0.80
Higher education by institution										
University	0.18	0.27	0.03	0.09	0.14	0.19	0.18	0.30	0.36	0.52
Academic college	0.10	0.23	0.03	0.12	0.07	0.26	0.12	0.29	0.18	0.23
Academic college for education	0.06	0.05	0.01	0.03	0.04	0.06	0.07	0.07	0.11	0.06
Technology school	0.07	0.06	0.05	0.08	0.08	0.07	0.09	0.05	0.07	0.04
Haredi women's teacher college	—	0.07	—	0.05	—	0.09	—	0.09	—	0.07
Degree study major										
Humanities	0.06	0.06	0.02	0.02	0.05	0.05	0.08	0.07	0.10	0.10
Social sciences	0.11	0.22	0.03	0.12	0.12	0.22	0.13	0.28	0.16	0.28
Natural sciences	0.10	0.20	0.01	0.05	0.03	0.15	0.09	0.23	0.27	0.40
Completed first degree	0.28	0.41	0.04	0.14	0.17	0.36	0.34	0.49	0.52	0.65
University	0.12	0.20	0.01	0.04	0.06	0.11	0.12	0.21	0.27	0.43
Academic college	0.11	0.17	0.03	0.08	0.07	0.19	0.15	0.22	0.18	0.19
Academic college for education	0.05	0.04	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.06	0.07	0.06	0.08	0.03

Source: Blass, Maagan, Mevarech, and Rapp, Taub Center | Data: CBS

Appendix Table 5. Findings from a regression model: Estimates of the factors explaining the academic achievements of PISA examinees by PISA reading quartile

Model	High school achievements				Psychometric exams		Higher education	
	Eligible for a Bagrut certificate	Eligible for a Bagrut certificate that meets higher education admission threshold	Mean Bagrut score	Mean Bagrut score including bonus	Took the psychometric exam	General psychometric score	Entrance to higher education	Completed first degree
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)
SES								
SES	0.203	0.216	0.150	0.166	0.211	0.249	0.225	0.197
Gender (Reference group: Girls)								
Boys	-0.017	-0.008	-0.037	-0.025	-0.056	0.191	-0.076	-0.141
Sector (Reference group: Arabic speaking)								
Hebrew speaking	0.039	0.008	0.087	0.050	-0.148	0.264	0.083	0.033
PISA Reading Proficiency Level quartile (Reference group: Quartile 1)								
PRP 2	0.234	0.200	0.240	0.250	0.139	0.088	0.188	0.138
PRP 3	0.344	0.361	0.411	0.446	0.283	0.315	0.284	0.236
PRP4	0.420	0.504	0.618	0.675	0.441	0.630	0.404	0.353
Constant	0.312	0.150	63.756	68.653	0.283	381.822	0.196	0.198
N	5,634	5,634	4,833	4,833	5,634	2,205	5,634	5,634
Adjusted R ²	0.224	0.2881	0.3274	0.3806	0.2392	0.4564	0.2442	0.2001

Notes: All models are estimated in OLS. The beta coefficients presented in the table are standardized coefficients. All coefficients are statistically significant at $p < 0.0001$, except for the values marked in purple, which indicate a significance level of $p < 0.05$, and the values marked in red, which are not statistically significant.

Source: Blass, Maagan, Mevarech, and Rapp, Taub Center | Data: CBS